

Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 10 (-2147483647 up to 2147483647)

**A.E. Bras
V.H.J. van der Velden**

Laboratory Medical Immunology (LMI), Department of Immunology, Erasmus Medical Center, Erasmus University, Rotterdam, the Netherlands
Correspondence: a.e.bras@gmail.com / a.bras@erasmusmc.nl / v.h.j.vandervelden@erasmusmc.nl

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Historic Overview

Decimal Crazy Sequential Representations

Inder Taneja published five papers on arXiv (for 1 up to 11111):

ARXIV Version	Evaluated Range	Allowed Operations	Missing Increasing	Missing Decreasing	Valid Representations
1 (06-02-2013) ¹	44 to 1000	+ * ^	2	10	1902 (of 1914)
2 (19-03-2013) ²	44 to 4444	+ * ^	50	53	8699 (of 8802)
3 (05-06-2013) ³	44 to 11111	+ * ^ ()	590	605	20941 (of 22136)
4 (05-08-2013) ⁴	0 to 11111	+ * ^ () -	449	315	21460 (of 22224)
5 (08-01-2014) ⁵	0 to 11111	+ * ^ () - /	9	10	22205 (of 22224)

Authors published three papers on Figshare/Zenodo (for -2147483647 up to 2147483647):

Date	Title
12-06-2018	Crazy Sequential Representations: Exhaustive Search ⁶
14-06-2018	Crazy Sequential Representations: Negative Integers ⁷
18-06-2018	Crazy Sequential Representations: Without Subtraction and/or Division ⁸

Inder Taneja published three papers on RGMIA (for 11112 up to 30000):

Date	Title
12-09-2018	Crazy Representations of Natural Numbers From 11112 to 20000 ⁹
10-11-2018	Crazy Representations of Natural Numbers From 20001 to 25000 ¹⁰
10-11-2018	Crazy Representations of Natural Numbers From 25001 to 30000 ¹¹

Authors published one paper on Figshare/Zenodo (comparing results for 11112 up to 30000):

Date	Title
06-12-2018	Crazy Sequential Representations: 11112 up to 30000 ¹²

Inder Taneja published two papers on Zenodo (combining results for 11112 up to 30000):

Date	Title
18-01-2019	Crazy Representations of Natural Numbers From 11112 to 20000 ²⁸
03-02-2019	Crazy Representations of Natural Numbers From 20000 to 30000 ²⁹

Authors published fourteen papers on Figshare/Zenodo (improving our previous work):

Date	Title	Date	Title
14-12-2018	Simplifications (01) ¹³	23-07-2019	Fill the Gaps (07) ³⁷
24-12-2018	Fill the Gaps (01) ¹⁴	30-07-2019	Fill the Gaps (08) ³⁸
02-01-2019	Fill the Gaps (02) ¹⁵	02-08-2019	Simplifications (02) ³⁹
28-01-2019	Fill the Gaps (03) ²⁵	08-08-2019	Fill the Gaps (09) ⁴⁰
06-02-2019	Fill the Gaps (04) ³⁰	14-08-2019	Fill the Gaps (10) ⁴¹
07-02-2019	Fill the Gaps (05) ³¹	22-08-2019	Fill the Gaps (11) ⁴²
19-07-2019	Fill the Gaps (06) ³⁶	22-08-2019	Fill the Gaps (12) ⁴³

Authors published one paper on Figshare/Zenodo (combining results from our previous work):

Date	Title
05-09-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 10 (-2147483647 up to 2147483647) ⁴⁴

Historic Overview

Non-Decimal Crazy Sequential Representations

Tim Wylie published one paper on arXiv (focusing on bases 3 through 10):

Date	Title
11-10-2018	Crazy Sequential Representations of Numbers for Small Bases ¹⁶

Authors published six papers on Figshare/Zenodo (focusing on bases 11 through 16):

Date	Title
04-01-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 11 (0000 up to AAAA) ¹⁷
04-01-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 12 (0000 up to BBBB) ¹⁸
04-01-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 13 (0000 up to CCCC) ¹⁹
04-01-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 14 (0000 up to DDDD) ²⁰
04-01-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 15 (0000 up to EEEE) ²¹
04-01-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 16 (0000 up to FFFF) ²²

Authors published one paper on Figshare/Zenodo (completing the base 11 up to 16 series):

Date	Title
09-01-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 11 up to 16 (0000 up to XXXX) ²³

Authors published one paper on Figshare/Zenodo (extending the base 16 series):

Date	Title
04-01-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 16 (-FFFFFF up to FFFFF) ²⁴

Authors published two papers on Figshare/Zenodo (focusing on bases 17 through 62):

Date	Title
23-01-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 17 up to 36 (0000 up to #####) ²⁶
02-02-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 17 up to 62 (0000 up to #####) ²⁷

Authors published four papers on Figshare/Zenodo (focusing on bases 3 through 9):

Date	Title
13-02-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 9 (0000 up to 8888) ³²
18-02-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 8 (0000 up to 7777) ³³
18-02-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 7 (0000 up to 6666) ³⁴
18-02-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 3 up to 9 ³⁵

Examples - Decimal Crazy Sequential Representations

Two valid base 10 crazy sequential representations (increasing and decreasing):

2671₁₀	48₁₀
$1_{10}/2_{10}*(3_{10}-4_{10}+5_{10})^6+7_{10}*89_{10}$	$9_{10}^{(8_{10}-7_{10})}*6_{10}/(-5_{10}+4_{10}+3_{10})+21_{10}$

Examples - Non-Decimal Crazy Sequential Representations

Two valid base 11 crazy sequential representations, and their base 10 representation:

5491₁₀	4142₁₁	378₁₀	314₁₁
$-1_{11}/2_{11}*(3_{11}-4_{11}+5_{11})^6+7_{11}*89A$		$A9_{11}^{(8_{11}-7_{11})}*6_{11}/(-5_{11}+4_{11}+3_{11})+21_{11}$	
$-1_{10}/2_{10}*(3_{10}-4_{10}+5_{10})^6+7_{10}*1077_{10}$		$119_{10}^{(8_{10}-7_{10})}*6_{10}/(-5_{10}+4_{10}+3_{10})+21_{10}$	

Two valid base 12 crazy sequential representations, and their base 10 representation:

6853₁₀	3B71₁₂	419₁₀	2AB₁₂
$-1_{12}/2_{12}*(3_{12}-4_{12}+5_{12})^6+7_{12}*89A_{12}+B_{12}$		$B_{12}+A9_{12}^{(8_{12}-7_{12})}*6_{12}/(-5_{12}+4_{12}+3_{12})+21_{12}$	
$-1_{10}/2_{10}*(3_{10}-4_{10}+5_{10})^6+7_{10}*1270_{10}+11_{10}$		$11_{10}+129_{10}^{(8_{10}-7_{10})}*6_{10}/(-5_{10}+4_{10}+3_{10})+21_{10}$	

Two valid base 13 crazy sequential representations, and their base 10 representation:

8460₁₀	3B0A₁₃	605₁₀	377₁₃
$-1_{13}/2_{13}*(3_{13}-4_{13}+5_{13})^6+7_{13}*89A_{13}+BC_{13}$		$CB_{13}+A9_{13}^{(8_{13}-7_{13})}*6_{13}/(-5_{13}+4_{13}+3_{13})+21_{13}$	
$-1_{10}/2_{10}*(3_{10}-4_{10}+5_{10})^6+7_{10}*1479_{10}+155_{10}$		$167_{10}+139_{10}^{(8_{10}-7_{10})}*6_{10}/(-5_{10}+4_{10}+3_{10})+21_{10}$	

Two valid base 14 crazy sequential representations, and their base 10 representation:

12217₁₀	4649₁₄	302₁₀	178₁₄
$-1_{14}/2_{14}*(3_{14}-4_{14}+5_{14})^6+7_{14}*89A_{14}+BCD_{14}$		$D_{14}-CB_{14}+A9_{14}^{(8_{14}-7_{14})}*6_{14}/(-5_{14}+4_{14}+3_{14})+21_{14}$	
$-1_{10}/2_{10}*(3_{10}-4_{10}+5_{10})^6+7_{10}*1704_{10}+2337_{10}$		$13_{10}-179_{10}+149_{10}^{(8_{10}-7_{10})}*6_{10}/(-5_{10}+4_{10}+3_{10})+21_{10}$	

Two valid base 15 crazy sequential representations, and their base 10 representation:

14221₁₀	4331₁₅	530₁₀	255₁₅
$-1_{15}/2_{15}*(3_{15}-4_{15}+5_{15})^6+7_{15}*89A_{15}+BCD_{15}-E_{15}$		$ED_{15}-CB_{15}+A9_{15}^{(8_{15}-7_{15})}*6_{15}/(-5_{15}+4_{15}+3_{15})+21_{15}$	
$-1_{10}/2_{10}*(3_{10}-4_{10}+5_{10})^6+7_{10}*1945_{10}+2668_{10}-14_{10}$		$223_{10}-191_{10}+159_{10}^{(8_{10}-7_{10})}*6_{10}/(-5_{10}+4_{10}+3_{10})+21_{10}$	

Two valid base 16 crazy sequential representations, and their base 10 representation:

16148₁₀	3F14₁₆	4402₁₀	1132₁₆
$-1_{16}/2_{16}*(3_{16}-4_{16}+5_{16})^6+7_{16}*89A_{16}+BCD_{16}-EF_{16}$		$FED_{16}-CB_{16}+A9_{16}^{(8_{16}-7_{16})}*6_{16}/(-5_{16}+4_{16}+3_{16})+21_{16}$	
$-1_{10}/2_{10}*(3_{10}-4_{10}+5_{10})^6+7_{10}*2202_{10}+3021_{10}-239_{10}$		$4077_{10}-203_{10}+169_{10}^{(8_{10}-7_{10})}*6_{10}/(-5_{10}+4_{10}+3_{10})+21_{10}$	

Definition - Base 10 Crazy Sequential Representation

Valid mathematical expression, thus well-formed interpretable syntactic construct.
 Evaluation results in an integer value, thus a number without a fractional component.
 Notation as used by most programming languages, thus restricted to following characters:

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 + - * / ^ ()

Digits 1 up to 9 occur in **increasing** or **decreasing** order:

$-1/2*(3-4+5)^6+7*89$ $9^{(8-7)*6}/(-5+4+3)+21$

Digits represent **single-digit** or **multi-digit** numbers (concatenation of digits is allowed):

$-1/2*(3-4+5)^6+7*89$ $9^{(8-7)*6}/(-5+4+3)+21$

Numbers occur in **positive form** or **negative form** (negation of numbers by “-” is allowed).

$-1/2*(3-4+5)^6+7*89$ $9^{(8-7)*6}/(-5+4+3)+21$

Allowed operations; **addition**, **subtraction**, **multiplication**, **division** and/or **exponentiation**.

$-1/2*(3-4+5)^6+7*89$ $9^{(8-7)*6}/(-5+4+3)+21$

Order of evaluation may be influenced by **parentheses** (also nested parentheses).

$-1/2*(3-4+5)^6+7*89$ $9^{(8-7)*6}/(-5+4+3)+21$

Representations with **negation** of **segments in parentheses** are referred to as “pseudo”.

$(1+2-3)*(45^*-(6^7)+8-9)$	$(98+7^*-(6^5)+4)*(3-2-1)$
$(1+2-3)*(45/- (6^7)+8-9)$	$(98+7/- (6^5)+4)*(3-2-1)$
$(1+2-3)*(45^- (6^7)+8-9)$	$(98+7^- (6^5)+4)*(3-2-1)$
$(-(1+2)+3)*(45^(6^7)+8-9)$	$(98+7^(6^5)+4)*(-(3-2)+1)$
$-(1-2+234*(6-(7+8-9)))$	$-((9-(8+7-6))*543-2+1)$

Representations without negation of segments in parentheses are referred to as “genuine”.

Note

Authors consider CSR to be proof-of-work, as identification is computationally expensive, while verification is trivial. Authors do not guaranty:

- Published CSR are the shortest in existence.
- Published CSR are in their simplest form.
- Unavailable CSR do not exists.

Overview

Within the -2147483647 up to 2147483647 range, increasing CSR are available for 1862330 integers and decreasing CSR are available for 2667352 integers:

	Increasing +CSR	Increasing -CSR	Decreasing +CSR	Decreasing -CSR
Genuine	928839	925488	1333456	1310678
Pseudo*	2326	5677	220	22998
Total	931165	931165	1333676	1333676

*pseudo CSR in case no genuine CSR available

Supplements

Increasing CSR were tabulated in the first supplement, for example:

Integer	Increasing CSR	Integer	Increasing CSR
1	$1^{23456789}$	-1	$-1^{23456789}$
2	$1^{234567-8+9}$	-2	$1-2^{345+678+9}$
3	$1^{2^{345}-678-9}$	-3	$123-45+6-78-9$
4	$1^{2345/6^{78-9}}$	-4	$1^{2345+67-8^{*9}}$
• • •	• • •	• • •	• • •
2147483644	$-12/3+4^{(5+6-7)^{8^9}}$	-2147483644	$12/3-4^{(5+6-7)^{8^9}}$
2147483645	$(-1+2^{34+56-7})/8-9$	-2147483645	$1+2+(3-4^{5-6+7})^{8^9}$
2147483646	$-1-2^{34}/(5-6-7)+8-9$	-2147483646	$1^{2-(34-5-6-7)^{8^9}}$
2147483647	$-1+2^{(34^{5-67-8^{*9}})}$	-2147483647	$1-2^{(34^{5-67-8^{*9}})}$

Decreasing CSR were tabulated in the second supplement, for example:

Integer	Decreasing CSR	Integer	Decreasing CSR
1	$(9-8)^{7654321}$	-1	$98-76-54+32-1$
2	$98-76-54/3-2^1$	-2	$98/7^{6-54-32^1}$
3	$9+87-6-54-32-1$	-3	$98/7-6^5/432+1$
4	$98-7-65-43+21$	-4	$9+87-65-4-32+1$
• • •	• • •	• • •	• • •
2147483644	$(9-8+7)^{(6+5)/4-3-2+1}$	-2147483644	$(-9+8-7)^{(6+5)/4+3+2-1}$
2147483645	$(9-8+7)^{(6+5)/4-3^{(2-1)}}$	-2147483645	$(-9+8-7)^{(6+5)/4+3/(2-1)}$
2147483646	$(9-8+7)^{(6+5)/4-3+2-1}$	-2147483646	$(-9+8-7)^{(6+5)/4+3-2+1}$
2147483647	$(9+8-7+6)^{(5+4)/32-1}$	-2147483647	$9-8-(7-6+5-4)^{(32-1)}$

Pseudo CSR were marked, for example:

Integer	Increasing CSR	Integer	Increasing CSR
230877	$(1234^{(5+6)+7})^{(8+9)}$	-230877	$(1234^{(-5-6)-7})^{(8+9)}$
230879 (P)	$-(1-2^3)^{4+5^{*6}^{(7+8-9)}}$	-230879	$(1+2^{*3})^{4-5^{*6}^{(7+8-9)}}$
230881	$(1-23)^{4-5^{(67+8)^{*9}}}$	-230881 (P)	$-(1-23)^{4+5^{(67+8)^{*9}}}$
230886	$(123+4)^{(5^{*6}^{*7-8})^{*9}}$	-230886	$(-123-4)^{(5^{*6}^{*7-8})^{*9}}$

Ranges

For the following ranges, genuine CSR were identified for each integer (top 10 shown):

Genuine Increasing CSR		
From	To	Length
1	10957	10957
10959	13963	3005
134217011	134218445	1435
16005	17311	1307
14799	15970	1172
19167	19885	719
51882890	51883528	639
34683	35283	601
5764509	5765093	585
13965	14539	575

Genuine Decreasing CSR		
From	To	Length
1	14323	14323
14325	17796	3472
43045843	43047599	1757
19821	21093	1273
54093	54922	830
18873960	18874776	817
117245	118053	809
23021	23793	773
2096770	2097534	765
21500	22254	755

Visualization

Cumulative density for the integers with at least one genuine CSR available:

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